

TUTORS' FACTORS INFLUENCING QUALITY IN PUBLIC PRIMARY TEACHERS TRAINING COLLEGES IN RIFT VALLEY, KENYA

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to establish tutors' factors influencing quality in public primary teachers training colleges in Rift Valley Zone, Kenya. This study was based on the Malcolm Knowles (1968) Theory of Andragogy of adult learning which postulates that adult learning is self-directed and is expected to take responsibility for their decision. The study used descriptive survey research design and the instruments for data collection were questionnaires, interviews and document analysis. Purposive, stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to select study sample. The target population was 2116 from all 4 Public Primary Teacher Training Colleges in Rift Valley Zone. Purposive technique was used to select 4 Principals, 4 Deans of Curriculum, 4 Deans of Students and the second year teacher trainees. Simple random sampling was employed to select 101 teacher trainers and 497 teacher trainees to represent 30% of the target population. A stratified sampling technique was used to select tutors and trainees according to gender and subject option A or B. The total sample population size was 610 respondents. Validity and Reliability of the research instruments were pre-tested through a pilot study in Asumbi TTC, a public TTC outside Rift Valley Zone. Data collected was analyzed and presented using descriptive statistics like tables and bar graphs generated with the aid of SPSS. The study found that the teacher educators in TTCs in Rift Valley Zone were competent in their subjects through experience although majority had trained to teach in secondary schools. This research recommends that the MOE come up with a national curriculum/central induction course for teacher educators in TTCs.

Keywords: tutors' factors, quality and teachers training college, primary education

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1. Introduction

Teacher Education is an important component of education as it influences all aspects of education (Kafu, 2011). The aspect of quality education and by extension the quality of teacher training has not been a key factor in the education spheres worldwide (UNESCO, 2007). There is no uniformity in training tutors. However, some countries like Ethiopia, Namibia and USA have both formal and informal continuing professional development programs for teacher educators combining college-based learning, MOE (2011). The United Nations Millennium Declaration's commitment to achieve UPE by 2015 was directly and simply set without explicit reference or regard to quality (UNESCO, 2007). This skewed approach has negative impact on the quality of training, teaching and learning in all levels of education including Primary Teacher Training Colleges.

Since independence, there have been commissions and strategic plans and policies on education with specific highlights on teacher quality. They include Ominde Commission of 1964, which observed that the provision of well educated, competent, respected and contented teaching force is by far the most important contribution the government can make to schools in Kenya. The Gachathi Report of 1976 pinpointed that there was need to improve the quality of teachers and teacher education by giving priority to mathematics, science, language, art, music, home science, agriculture and science in recruitment for training as teachers. The Kamunge Report of 1988 recommended that students for pre-service primary teacher training programme be recruited from candidates who choose teaching as a career and be admitted to teachers colleges following the completion of secondary education. The Master Plan on Education and Training (MPET) of 1998 emphasized that there was need to improve teacher quality by putting in place appropriate mechanism for selection into college. The Koech Report of 1999 called Totally Integrated Quality Education and Training (TIQET) advocated that the admission criteria for teacher training be divided to ensure that subject specialization is provided for. All these recommendations referred to above have one thing in common, they are all concerned about quality, specialization and standard which have been challenging to accomplish in TTC.

Furthermore, The Constitution of Kenya (2010) in Article 43 (f), states that every person has the right to education. Article 237 (3a) mandates the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) to review the standards of education and training of persons entering the teaching service and (3c) advice the national government on matters relating to teaching profession. According to MOE (2011), for Kenya to realize a globally competitive system, well qualified teachers are required in classrooms at all levels through uplifting standards of training teachers. With this over view of teacher

education and training, this study intends to investigate factors influencing quality teacher training in Public Teacher Training Colleges in Rift Valley Zone, in Kenya.

2. Literature Review

The quality of education, to a greater extent depends on the quality of teachers produced in TTCs. An adequate supply of well trained teachers is critical to improvements in education. Good practice in teaching is a complex process which requires a great deal of different knowledge namely, the content knowledge that is knowing about the subject matter to be taught; pedagogic knowledge that is knowing how to engage with learners and to manage a classroom and pedagogical content knowledge which involves knowing how to present and formulate the subject matter Akyeampong (2011). The international day for teachers is celebrated world over every 5th October. This ought to one of days set aside for rewarding teachers with the highest achievement in various fields. Unfortunately, this has not happened to our local teachers (UNESCO, 1997).

Quality training contributes significantly to quality education. It is imperative to have adequately prepared and motivated tutors in colleges who would in turn train trainees qualitatively in all aspects. According to Msita (2008), teachers are implementers of educational innovation who operate as "foot soldiers". Thus, they face a lot of challenges as they give hand in any educational transformation. Tutors are used to implement even unpiloted recommendations and policies which is a difficult task. However, newly appointed tutors should be inducted or made familiar with working environment and the fellow employees (Saleemi, 2007). According to MOEST (2011), teachers are highly educated. However, they often have little knowledge and experience of the professional area of primary education or the reality of primary teaching. Most tutors have a B. ED or Dip. Ed. and were initially trained as secondary school teachers with a specialty in particular subject areas. Most experienced secondary teachers are posted to PTTCs or as fresh graduates. In either case they often have little knowledge and skill of primary education, as a result their courses are often taught as abstract and theoretical regardless of multifaceted primary school curriculum. This ultimately translates into poor training of trainees by tutors.

According to UNESCO (2007), teachers' earnings provide an incentive mechanism which can influence both the quality and motivation of teachers. If teachers' real average earnings had kept pace with other professional groups over period, the productivity impact of their earnings growth would likely have been small. In Kenya, teachers' salaries including tutors who are employed under TSC earn relatively low wages than counterparts in other professions thus lowering their morale which translate into low quality training of teachers. Trainers should employ productive

practices such as team work and initiate enabling working environment to facilitate quality training in college. Teachers should work in a team so as to encourage the sharing of the knowledge or ideas (UNESCO, 1997).

Continuous professional development of tutors has not been formally undertaken. Although tutors have already trained basically and may have some experience as a result of accidental and unwilling compulsory on job training, they should be dynamic. The main focus of teacher education continues while on pre-service training, in service updating and renewal of knowledge, skills and capabilities in now widely acknowledged as a high priority (MOE, 2009). Teachers are a key enabling factor in improving the quality of education and preparing them begins with the selection of those who are to enter teacher training colleges. Fullan (1991) states that if the teacher as an advocate can become skilled at integrating the change and the change process, he or she can become one of the most powerful forces of change. Teachers play a unique and demanding role in eliciting responses from the students for curriculum development based on student's voices. It is not the input from the teachers themselves, that the strategy deems more important rather it is the role in promoting authentic participation of their students in the process. Thus, the role of the teacher in curriculum delivery is very important which encompasses their training. There has been major curriculum innovation in Kenya, for instance the establishment of 8-4-4 in 1984 facilitated one in 1986. In 1992, the review of the Primary and Secondary curriculum necessitated curriculum innovation in 1994. The reviews are usually necessitated by the need to make the curriculum reflect and respond to the changes in the society as emphasized in various educations (MOE 2003).

There is deeper understanding of how teacher educator can support and challenge future teachers in their ability to think critically and thoughtfully in developing their identities as future educators (Rot, 2011). It is therefore imperative for the teacher educators to inculcate critical thinking and futuristic aspects in teacher trainees. USAID (2006), observed that much of teacher training in Pakistan remain irrelevant to their classroom where trainees are to employ their skills. Different functionaries are responsible for delivering trainings but there are no mechanisms that exist in order to facilitate such linkages. This scenario is also experienced in Kenya whereby there is no distinct corresponding review and consequent implementation of syllabus under Directorate of Basic Education. The quality of instruction is one of the most important determinants of the level of learning achievements; quality teacher training impact on the quality of teaching and learning in institutions. According to Nafukho (2002), training involves transfer of skills, knowledge, behavior and attitudes and in order to have competent employees, hence training is a must. The concept of quality training is examined in various areas such as issues relating to trainers, trainees, T/L resources and administration.

3. Research Objective

The main objective of this study is to investigate tutors' factors influencing quality in public primary teachers training colleges in Rift Valley, Kenya

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design

Research design can be regarded as an arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance with the research purpose. It is the conceptual structure within, which research is conducted. It constitutes the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data (Kothari 2003, Kombo & Tromp, 2009). This study employed descriptive survey design. This is a method of collecting information by interviewing or administering questionnaires to a sample of individuals. It is commonly used to collect information about people's attitude, opinions, habits or any of the variety of education of social issues (Orodho, 2009). This study adopted descriptive survey research design due to its appropriateness since it involves collection of data and descriptive of the characteristics of the population, which forms the basis of this study (Mugenda & Mugenda, 1999). The major purpose of descriptive research is description of the state of affairs as it exists at present (Kothari, 2008).

4.2 Target Population

Target population refers to all the members of a real or hypothetical set of people, events or objects to which the researcher wishes to generalize the results of the study (Orodho 2009) after testing the sample. The target population for the study was all the PTTCs in Rift Valley Zone, Principals, Deans of Students, Deans of Curriculum, Tutors and second year students. They were all relevant to the study because they undertake the TTC curriculum in Kenya as implementers and participants in Kenya TTCs. They were selected on the basis of administration and teaching/learning involvement. The second year trainees were targeted because they have been in college long enough and that the option A and B affects them specifically unlike the first year teacher trainees who cover all subjects.

4.3 Instrumentation

Research instruments refer to tools used for collecting data and how those tools are developed (Oso & Onen 2009). Kothari (2008) advocates that the researcher should select methods of collecting data taking into consideration the nature of investigation, objective and scope of the inquiry, financial resources, available time and the desired degree of accuracy. According to Orodho (2009), there are four critical considerations

while constructing research instruments, namely the objectives of the study, the types of population/sample, the geographical distribution of subjects and the nature of questionnaire items. This study adopted a descriptive research design, which employed the use of questionnaire, interview, observation and documentary analysis. The selection of tools was arrived at considering the nature of the data to be collected, the time available, the objective of the study and the type of sampled population.

4.4 Procedure

The data collection procedures were logistical issues related to the study. They were divided into three categories namely: pre-fieldwork logistics, fieldwork logistic and post fieldwork logistics (Orodho, 2009). Pre-fieldwork logistics which refers to specific considerations before data collection to be undertaken was to write/prepare a proposal, work plan protocol, budget and research instruments and obtain research permit. Research permit was sought from National Council for Science and Technology (NCST) which enabled the researcher to collect data in the selected PTTCs in Rift Valley Zone.

Post-fieldwork logistics are all the activities that a researcher must undertake after the fieldwork. It included collecting instruments from the field, editing them ready for coding and analysis. During data collection, the researcher was focused, informed the respondents of the nature and intended use of data, kept information collected confidential, applied appropriate techniques, controlled statistical disclosure, maintained punctuality in appointments, friendliness, simplicity, considered questions that elicited appropriate response and acknowledged psychological factors like fear that induces incorrect responses (Kombo & Tromp, 2006).

4.5 Data Analysis

The data was collected by use of questionnaires, interview schedules and documentary analysis. The collected data was analyzed and interpreted by use of descriptive statistics which uses measure of central tendency (such as the mean) and distributions (frequencies and percentages). Data collected was presented on tables and bar graphs. The data was analyzed using descriptive analysis, where frequencies, percentages and tables were generated, with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). This design was suitable to this study as information was collected using interview from principals and Deans (DOCs and DOSs) and the questionnaires from the 2nd year's students and tutors

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Gender of teacher educators and teacher trainees

The policy of gender equity is supposed to be upheld by all sectors of the Ministry of Education, TTCs inclusive. The major respondents were therefore asked to indicate their gender as in Table 1.

Table 1: Gender of teacher educators and Teacher Trainees

Gender	Teacher Educators		Teacher Trainees	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	66	65.3	248	49.9
Female	35	34.7	249	50.1
Total	101	100	497	100

Table 4.2 shows that the teacher educators' response per gender as 65.5% and 34.7%, male and female respectively implying that policy on gender equity is either disregarded or not yet implemented fully by TSC in staffing. This scenario may have resulted from the deployment of secondary school Principals who mainly happen to be male teachers. The gender of teacher trainees shows that 49.3% and 50.7% of the teacher trainees' respondents were male and females respectively indicating gender equity in college admission. This result relates to Lewin (2004) emphasize that quality as an integral component of meaningful and realistic education ought to have been underscored with equal magnitude as access and gender equity.

5.2 Age distribution of teacher educators

Demand and supply of labour force is a key component in an organization like TTCs. Age factor thus need to be considered in reference to the expected number of retirements and replacements correspondingly in order to maintain and increase quality production of teachers. Teacher educators were therefore asked to state their age as in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Age distribution of teacher educators

Gender	Age distribution of educators				Total
	25-35 yrs	36-44 yrs	45-54 yrs	>55 yrs	
Male	5(5.0)	34(33.7)	25(24.8)	2(2.0)	66(65.3)
Female	7(6.9)	13(12.9)	15(14.9)	0(0.0)	35(34.7)
Total	12(11.9)	47(46.5)	40(39.6)	2(2.0)	101

Most teacher educators as seen in Table 4.3 are in the age bracket of 36 to 54 years. These categories make up 86.1% of the sampled educators. The 11.9% (5.0% & 6.9%) in age bracket of 25-35 year expected to replace potential retirees in the next 10 years (45-

54yrs) is far much inadequate. The qualification of teacher educators is shown in Table 4.4

5.3 Qualification of teacher educators

For an individual to work in any field of education as a teacher, one must have specific qualifications. It was therefore imperative to ask teacher educators to indicate their qualification academically and professionally as shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Qualification of teacher educators

Level	Academic qualification		Professional qualification (Education)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
PhD	2	2.0	1	1.0
Masters	34	33.7	30	29.7
Bachelors	56	55.4	60	59.4
Diploma	7	6.9	7	6.9
Others	2	2.0	3	3.0
Total	101	100	101	100

Table 4.4 shows that most of the teacher educators hold bachelor's degree in academics (55.4%) and the teaching profession (59.4%) implying that tutors were progressive in their teaching career. There are 91.1% trainers with Bachelors in academic qualification and 90.1% in professional qualifications. This co-relation implies that most tutors advance professionally thus boosting their level of competency. The 1.0% (91.1% - 90.1%) difference indicates those who did not undertake education nor had professional qualification as tutors lower the level of competency of teacher educators insignificantly.

5.4 Teaching experience of teacher educators

Work output or productivity to a greater extent depends on appropriate experiences. Thus, it was necessary to establish the experiences of the teacher educators in totality and specifically in TTC as indicated in Table 4.5

Table 4.5: Teaching experience of teacher educators

Teaching experience in general			Experience as a Tutor in TTC		
Years	Frequency	Percent	Years	Frequency	Percent
<5 yrs	01	1.0	<3 yrs	09	8.9
6-10 yrs	11	10.9	4-7 yrs	37	36.6
11-15 yrs	21	20.8	8-11 yrs	23	22.8
>15 yrs	68	67.3	>12 yrs	32	31.7
Total	101	100	Total	101	100

Table 4.5 shows that majority of the teacher educators have over 15 years teaching experience in general (67.3%). However, most of the teacher educators have experience of between 4 and 11 years in TTC. This comprised a total of 59.4% (36.6% & 22.8%) which is inadequate experience limiting level of competency of tutors in TTC. This results are in line (MOE, 2009)'s observation that continuous professional development of tutors has not been formally undertaken. Although tutors have already trained basically and may have some experience as a result of accidental and unwilling compulsory on job training, they should be dynamic.

5.5 Age distribution of teacher trainees

The age of teacher trainee is of concern in regard to facilitation, understanding their diversity, creation of conducive and enabling learning environment by TTCs. They were therefore asked to give their ages as illustrated in Fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Age distribution of student respondents

Key

- | | | |
|-------------|-------------|-----------|
| 16-20 yrs 1 | 26-30yrs 3 | >36 yrs 5 |
| 21-25 yrs 2 | 31-35 yrs 4 | |

The majority of the teacher trainees were between the ages of 21 and 25 as shown in Fig 4.1. This implies that they are adults by Kenya law. However, they are still in stormy adolescence stage which is challenging in terms of discipline and behavior control impacting on quality teacher training negatively.

5.6 KCSE grade of the teacher trainees

One of the cardinal requirements of P1 course is a KCSE certificate from KNEC. The admission grade by the MOE to TTC is C. The trainers were asked to indicate their KCSE grade as shown in Fig. 4.2.

Fig. 4.2: KCSE grade of teacher trainees

Most of the trainees scored a mean grade of C+ (minimum university entry) at the KCSE level which means that with adequate resources they are potential university students. Most of them feel they should have been at the university and so they are less motivated to be in college undertaking P1 Course which is lowly rated. The governments need to be proactive and come up with pragmatic strategies to facilitate their rightful education.

5.7 Subject Option Distribution in second year

The P1 course takes two years. In the first year, trainees cover all the subjects combined and seat for a Mid-course examination. The average for only two subjects (math & I. Science), out of thirteen subjects (2/10) are used to determine option placement in second year. The trainees were consequently asked to state their option (A or B) as indicated in Table 4.6

Table 4.6: Subject Option Distribution in second year

Option	Frequency	Percent
Option A (Science oriented)	253	50.9
Option B (Humanity oriented)	244	49.1
Total	497	100

Table 4.6 indicates that option 'A' (50.9%) is slightly higher/more preferred than option 'B' (49.1%) This conforms to administrator's observation that sciences are held with high esteem and superior to humanities. Furthermore, optioning criterion is skewed towards sciences in that math and Integrated Sciences mean is used for placement (KTCPA, 2006). This inclination may affect a number of trainees in propagation of talents and future advancement in education. A more comprehensive approach is required in optioning. It should consider aspects such as:

- a) trainee's ability, attitude and feelings on teaching career development;
- b) availability of tutors and subject trained and teaching combination;
- c) adequacy of College facilities and cost per head training;
- d) future prospects of trainees including university education;
- e) applicability/prospective market availability for the options subject;
- f) talented and gifted trainees.

Otherwise, why undertake training on the basis of option A and B while it is not considered during teaching practice and the actual employment in teaching profession.

5.8 The level of competency of teacher educators

The first objective of the study was to establish the level of competency of teacher trainers. The teacher educators and teacher trainees were asked to show their agreement to the statements shown in Table 4.7

Table 4.7: The level of Competency of teacher educators

Statement	Teacher educators						Teacher Trainees					
	Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Have knowledge on the subject content	98	97.0	0	0	3	3.0	422	84.9	18	3.6	57	11.5
Subject effectively taught	78	77.3	6	6.0	17	16.7	307	61.9	41	8.2	149	29.9
Integration of emerging/crosscutting issues done in teaching subject	85	84.1	7	7.0	9	8.9	314	63.2	84	16.9	99	19.9
Timely use of latest teaching approaches to deliver subject content	69	68.4	18	17.8	14	13.8	261	52.5	56	11.3	180	36.2
Examination administration and management done with ease	92	91.0	4	4.0	5	5.0	344	69.2	35	7.0	118	23.8
Teaching Practice assessment undertaken smoothly	93	92.0	2	2.0	6	6.0	374	75.2	23	4.6	100	20.2

5.9 Knowledge on the subject content

From Table 4.7, a total of 97% of teacher educators and 84.9% of teacher trainees agreed that tutors were knowledgeable while 3.0% and 11.5% of teacher educators and teacher trainees respectively disagreed that tutors have knowledge on the subject content they teach which is critical. The deficiency could be attributed to lack of initial training or induction of tutors, individual tutor's negligence, failure to research or study further (use of yellow notes) and lack of teaching learning resources/facilities

The college principals interviewed asserted that there was no initial training on teacher education given to tutors in TTC. There was no uniform, clearly organized curriculum or central/national program to undergo before being posted/deployed or redeployed as teacher trainers. They train and gain experience on the job. Basically they trained to teach in secondary schools in two subject specialization plus professional Education units. The same observations were echoed by DOCs and DOSs. Although, there was primary option in KU, it did not effectively meet the demands- supply of tutors to colleges. Most tutors are university graduates. About 90% don't have basic training for TTC training. Competence is gained through seminars workshops, programs. MOE through her SAGAs, (KIE, TSC KNEC& KESI), USAID and TEPDC, carry out capacity building. About 75% of lecturers have 15 years experience.

However, one of the DOCs reiterated that majority of tutors are good and there are three categories of tutors Trained for Primary Teacher Education (1) through primary option, (2) BED – majority trained teach in secondary schools and (3) Formerly primary School teachers – upcoming group trained to teach primary school, but furthered education and posted to colleges. Readership of lecturer have improved and a

good number have undertaken further education, post graduate, middle management courses, masters and even PhDs.

The finding agrees with Akyeampong (2011) who stated that the quality of education, to a greater extent depends on the quality of teachers produced in TTCs. An adequate supply of well trained teachers is critical to improvements in education. Good practice in teaching is a complex process which requires a great deal of different knowledge namely, the content knowledge that is knowing about the subject matter to be taught; pedagogic knowledge that is knowing how to engage with learners and to manage a classroom and pedagogical content knowledge which involves knowing how to present and formulate the subject matter. The same results relate to UNESCO (2005), who observed that quality training, contributes significantly to quality education. It is therefore paramount to have adequately prepared and motivated tutors in colleges. They in turn train trainees qualitatively who are consequently knowledgeable, skilled and committed. Teachers dedicated to children's learning, lead to good quality education.

5.10 Subject effectively taught

There were 77.3% of teacher educators and 61.9% of teacher trainee agreed that tutors were effective in subject content delivery. On the contrary 16.7% and 29.9% of the teacher Educators and teacher trainees respectively disagreed on the same while 6% and 8.2% were undecided whether subject content teaching was effective. This implies that there is need for more or continuous updating of respective subject tutors to improve their level of competency.

From the interview carried out some of the respondents, one of the DOS remarked that most tutors are competent in subject content while they gain experience on methodology as they train trainees. Although tutors are not trained, they have learned through experience and trial and error before being inducted. Those inducting however, if they were not properly, inducted pass wrong information to incoming tutors. TPEDC program has brought positive change though it may not be as effective as having a national centralized tutor/teacher educator training or induction

The result coincides with the MOEST (2011), claim that teachers are highly educated. However, they often have little knowledge and experience of the professional area of primary education or the reality of primary teaching. Most tutors have a B. ED or Dip. Ed. and were initially trained as secondary school teachers with a specialty in particular subject areas. Most experienced secondary teachers are posted to PTTCs or as fresh graduates. In either case, they often have little knowledge of primary level of education, as a result their courses are often taught as abstract and theoretical regardless of multifaceted primary school curriculum. This ultimately translates into poor training of trainees by tutors. The same finding is in line with Lewin (2004) who

argued that, consideration should also be given to people who train teachers. They tend to be recruited from the ranks of practicing mid-career teachers, and many stay in teacher training until retirement gradually losing contact with schools/institutions. This problem is exacerbated by a preference for secondary school teachers who are seldom familiar with realities of primary education. A possible solution could be short-term appointments of experienced primary school teachers to be teacher trainers or provision of centralized induction or training of college tutors.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study has established that most tutors have very good mastery of their respective subject content. The teacher educators taught their subjects effectively, integrated emerging/crosscutting issues in subject content delivery, handled examinations with limited difficulties and undertook TP assessment with ease. Therefore, this study concluded that the teacher educators in TTCs in Rift valley zone are competent in their subjects through experience although the majority had trained to teach in secondary schools. This research based on its objectives makes the following recommendations: the college administrators (Principals, DOCs & DOSs) interviewed asserted that there was no initial training on teacher education given to tutors in TTC. There is no uniform, clearly organized curriculum or central/national program to undergo before being posted/deployed or redeployed as teacher trainers. They train and gain experience on the job. Basically, they trained to teach in secondary schools in two subject specialization plus professional Education units. Although, there was primary option in KU, it did not effectively meet the demands- supply of tutors to college. The findings were also corroborated by some tutors advocating for additional training for them to be effective in their subject content delivery. A few tutors were not competent in terms of effective subject content delivery, integrating of emerging/crosscutting issues, use of modern teaching approaches, examination administration and management and TP assessment. There is no standard induction implying that it is done on trial and error lowering level of competency of tutors at an appropriate time. This study therefore recommends that MOE to come up with a curriculum or a central induction course or INSET programme for teacher educators before posting/deployment to TTCs.

References

1. Akyeampong, W. (2011). Teacher preparation and continuing professional Development. University of Sussex.
2. Fullan, B. (1986). Raising school quality in developing countries: What investments boots learning. Washington Dc World Bank. Discussion Paper.

3. Gachathi, P. (1976). *Report of the National Committee on Educational Objective and Policies*. Government Printers Nairobi, Kenya.
4. Kafu, P.A. (2011). Education in Kenya. Emerging Issues. Retrieved from <http://www.muk.ac.ke/ijci/>, www.muk.ac.ke/./kafufulltext.pdf
5. Kamunge J. (1988). Report of the Presidential Working Party on Education and Manpower Training for the Next Decade and Beyond. Government Printers: Nairobi.
6. Kombo, D. K & Tromp, L. A. (2006). *Proposal and thesis writing: An introduction*: Pauline's Publication Africa: Nairobi (Kenya).
7. Kothari, C. R. (2008). *Research methodology*. New Age International Publishers.
8. MOE. (2011) .Teacher education professional development. Continuing professional development for teacher educator. Concept paper- draft 15th March 2011.
9. MOE. (2009). National primary teacher trainers' induction course: College level training of tutors - May 22nd to June 5th 2009. Government Printer: Nairobi.
10. Msita, V. (2008). Transforming teacher practice: A look at the experiences of two first-year teacher-learners in the NPDE Programme.
11. Mugenda, O. M., & Mugenda, A. G. (1999). *Research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches (Rev. Ed)*. Act Press: Nairobi.
12. Nafukho, F. M., & Kangethe, S. (2002). Training of trainers: Strategies for the 21st Century. Moi University Press, Printed by Fotoform Ltd: Nairobi.
13. Orodho A.J. (2009). Elements of education and social sciences: Research methods.
14. Oso, W. Y., & Onen, D. (2009). *A general guide to writing research proposal and report. A handbook of beginning researchers*. Jomo Kenyatta Foundation (JKF): Nairobi.
15. Rot, I. (2011). *Learning (not) to become a teacher: A qualification analysis of the job entrance issues*. Elsevier Ltd: South Africa.
16. Saleemi, N. (2007). Principles & practice of management simplified Rev. Ed. Acme Press (Kenya) Ltd: Nairobi.
17. UNESCO. (1997). Getting ready for the 21st century changes facing key players in the management and development of learning through education training. A vision that creates an even feature for Kenya. Held at Lillian Towers, Mawingo Hall on 25th February, 1997 (unpublished).
18. UNESCO. (2007). *Education For All in Africa*. Dakar Report Brenda Publication.
19. USAID. (2006). United States Agency for International Development: Teacher Education in Pakistan.

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